

Reviewer 2

This research examines the response of near surface temperature and wind speed and precipitation to the update of land cover category, particularly for central Mexico using the WRF model. This research could be an addition to the literature on the effect of land surface condition on the atmosphere. But before being published, this manuscript needs to be further improved to provide an insight into the mechanism behind the atmospheric differences caused by the land cover changes. Some examples needed to be improved are suggested in the specific comments.

We appreciate all your comments. After a careful revision of the manuscript that considered your comments and those from others anonymous reviewers, we consider that this version has greatly improved. Listed below is a description of the major modifications we made to the manuscript.

- The final part of the “Abstract” has been modified in order to clarify some points mentioned by the reviewers.
- In the section “1. Introduction”, we have modified two paragraphs and defined the objective in a scientific way and more explicitly. We have also added a paragraph that describes the content of the article.
- We have reorganized and added subsections in section “3. Methods and data”:
 - 3.1. Model configuration
 - 3.2. Description and assessment of the experiments
 - 3.3. Observational data
 - 3.4. LULC dataset
 - 3.4.1 Changes of LULC
- A subsection on section “4. Results and discussion” was added to discuss the physical processes involved.
- Section “5. Conclusions” was modified at the suggestion of removing some sentences.
- The citation of some references was revised and modified.
- LULC's change matrix was added in supplemental material.
- We have checked the manuscript for errors in English language and style.

In the following we reply to comments and suggestions step by step.

Note: Line numbers refer to the original manuscript.

Specific comments:

Line 21 on Page 1: Why do the authors particularly choose the months of January, April, July and September?

Response: Thanks for the observation and the reason was because the climate in the study area is characterized by two well-defined seasons: the dry season, which spans from November to April, and the rainy season, which runs from May to October. The dry season is subdivided into dry-hot, from March to May and the dry-cold, from November to February. In this way, the months used for the numerical simulations are representative of these climatic characteristics. We have added this explanation in the revised version of the manuscript (subsection 3.2).

Line 22 on Page 1: What do the authors analyze only near surface temperature and wind speed, and hourly precipitation?

Response: These variables are widely used by the operational weather forecasting system. In addition, these are also the three variables that are frequently reported in the literature.

Line 10 on Page 9: Do you mean 2-m surface temperature with near-surface temperature? Specifically, at which height does the temperature come from in the model and observation?

Response: Yes, the near-surface temperature is the 2-m surface temperature. Predicted temperature by WRF model is a temperature at 2-m (variable T2), and the meteorological station temperature sensor is located between 1.25 and 2m above ground level; in accordance with current Mexican regulations specified in the document “Weather stations, climatological and hydrological, part 2: Technical specifications to be

accomplished by the materials and measuring instruments for the automatic and conventional meteorological stations”
(<https://www.gob.mx/cms/uploads/attachment/file/166838/nmx-aa-166-2-scfi-2015.pdf>).

Lines 12 on Page 9: Why do the authors show the absolute value? The difference could be positive or negative. This reviewer thinks the sign could be meaningful particularly to understand the effect of land cover change on near-surface temperature.

Response: We appreciate the comment. The absolute difference was used because we thought that it was better to simply show the differences, without characterizing them as positive or negative. It is somewhat like MAE.

Fig.4: To this reviewer, the diurnal variations of the five days look very similar. Why don't you choose a 5-day period of very different diurnal variations?

Response: We apologize that the previous version had not been clear enough in what figure 4 represents. This figure shows the diurnal variability of the temperature but of the monthly average, that is, all the 5-day forecasts made for each day of January, in this case 31 forecasts of 120-hour (5-day). The analysis was performed every 24 hours: 1-24 h (Fig. 4a), 25-48 h (Fig. 4b), 49-72 h (Fig. 4c), 73-96 h (Fig. 4d), and 97-120 h (Fig. 4e), ie the first 24 hours simulated of each day of the month were analyzed to obtain the behavior of 1-24 h, then the following 48 simulated hours of each day were analyzed to obtain the behavior of the next 48 hours (25-48 h), this continued to be analyzed until the 120 hours forecast. The figure 4 shows the monthly diurnal variability in the shaded area and its average in the thick line. We have now complemented a more detailed description of the analysis in the revised version (subsection 3.2).

Fig. 7: Why do the authors choose only station 6? Could the findings be applied to the other stations?

Response: Showing only the behavior of one station was with the objective of not saturating the manuscript with many graphs with similar behavior. In addition, results are representative. Figure 7 predominantly shows an overestimation in wind speed when using USGS compared to NALCMS, and also this was observed in all the stations analyzed. In this way, the behavior shown in Figure 7 for a station is synthesized in Figure 8, through the use of the box plot, where the distribution of RMSEs for all stations is observed using USGS or NaLCMS.

Section 4.3: Precipitation is a resultant variable. By the update of land cover dataset, the difference of precipitation needs to be understood in terms of all the relevant processes for a scientific insight. However, this study seems to simply present the differences.

Response: We have now added an analysis of the atmospheric processes involved in section 4 (subsection 4.4). We hope that the revised version of the manuscript satisfies this comment.

Section 5. Conclusions: Instead of just summarizing the differences, could the authors present any meaningful, specific mechanisms behind the differences?

Response: Thanks for the recommendation. We have added subsection 4.4 in the revised version and hope that it helps in clarifying that key point mentioned above.